

ANALYSIS OF CHANGES IN HYDROGEOLOGICAL CONDITIONS AT DIFFERENT STAGES OF SOLID MINERAL MINING USING STOCHASTIC MODELING

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ABSTRACT: A transformation is currently underway in the global mining industry due to the depletion of easily accessible reserves of large near-surface deposits. This has led to the need to exploit smaller, medium-sized deposits with lower ore grades and reserves at significant depths in remote regions with complex geological and hydrogeological conditions. This study examines the hydrogeological conditions of two closely located major gold ore deposits that were actively mined in the latter half of the previous century but abandoned in the 1990s. Both pits and numerous underground mines are now almost entirely flooded, with pit No. 1 holding 9 million cubic meters of water and pit No. 2 containing 20 million cubic meters. Plans are in place to resume mining activities at one of these deposits soon. The analysis of archival materials and the construction of geofiltration and geomigration models were carried out for predictive calculations of water inflows during the dewatering of pit No. 1 and its subsequent exploitation to a depth of 270 meters. Additionally, hydrological modeling of surface runoff was conducted.

Key words: hydrogeological conditions, water table, groundwater, pit, forecast calculation.

INTRODUCTION

In the mid-20th century, the ore field under examination was a focal point for gold mining across the entirety of the Soviet Union. Administratively, the deposits are in the southern part of eastern Siberia, within the territory of the Russian Federation. The ore field is situated in a depression (graben) within a stretched depression oriented in a northeast direction and bounded by two ridges from the northwest and southeast. The absolute elevations of the depression range from +580 to +600 m, while the ridges range from +600 to +700 m. Two deposits and a tailings storage facility are closely located next to each other and separated by a river (see Fig. 1). The river valley is wide (up to 5 km), well developed, and consists of 5 terraces.

The climate of the region is sharply continental, characterized by long winters and short summers; sharp fluctuations in temperatures and atmospheric pressure within a single day; relatively low amounts of precipitation, especially in winter.

Figure 1. Diagram showing the layout of the main objects being studied on a satellite image and in a geological cross-section.

Brief description of the studied deposits

In terms of geological structure, the ore field is associated with a depression of Mesozoic graben, predominantly composed of gold-bearing sandstones and conglomerates of Upper Jurassic-Lower Cretaceous age, overlaying medium-composition effusions. At the base lies a poorly permeable layer of

metamorphic and intrusive rocks. Additional complexity arises from a thin layer of permafrost rocks developed on the northern slopes and numerous tectonic disruptions. The bedrock formations are covered by a mantle of loose Quaternary deposits up to 20 meters thick. In hydrogeological terms, the area is characterized by complex aquifer systems consisting of alluvial deposits and Mesozoic sedimentary-volcanic formations (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Schematic geological-hydrogeological profile of the study area

Mining operations began in 1948, initially focusing on underground extraction before transitioning to open-pit mining in the 1980s. Pit No. 1 reaches a depth of 100 meters, while Pit No. 2 reaches 150 meters. Both pits are interconnected through extensive underground workings. Figure 2 illustrates the layout of the pits and underground mine workings within the deposits. Dewatering of the deposits was managed through a centralized pumping system located at a depth of 250 meters, with the pumped-out water discharged into the river via a specially designed settling basin.

In the 1990s, the exploitation of the deposits ceased, and dewatering operations stopped. As a result, the quarries and numerous underground mine workings began filling with water and are now almost completely flooded.

The intensive development of the area has led to significant changes in the natural environment, resulting in the formation of anthropogenic relief. The surface of the southeastern part of deposit No. 1 is disrupted by a series of large collapse sinkholes that have formed above the underground mine workings left without proper support. The total subsidence of the area has now exceeded 5 meters.

At present, the technical condition of these underground mine workings is unknown, but some of them have collapsed, as evidenced by the area of subsidence spreading southeast of Pit No. 1, some of which are partially filled with water. On the other hand, while drilling numerous exploration boreholes, collapses without core were recorded, indicating the preservation of some workings. In any case, within these workings and nearby, there is a zone of disintegration characterized by increased permeability values compared to the main massif.

HYDROGEOLOGICAL MODELING

Geofiltration schematization

From the perspective of predicting water inflows into the pit, only the upper structural layer is of interest. The lower structural layer, the crystalline basement, can be considered generally impermeable to groundwater. The middle structural layer, predominated by lavas and pyroclastic formations, can be assumed to be of very low permeability.

Within the upper structural layer, two hydrogeological subdivisions are distinguished: the aquifer system of loose Quaternary deposits and the aquifer system of bedrock deposits of Jurassic-Cretaceous age and granite formations. Groundwater movement is mainly determined by interaction with the land surface - water recharge through infiltration and discharge into surface water bodies. For this reason, the boundaries of the developed model are preliminarily selected based on the surface water divides. The choice of the lower boundary is determined by the distribution of permeable rocks. Within the intermountain basin, the lower boundary corresponds to the base of sedimentary rocks. In the mountainous

framing, where granites and diorites outcrop on the surface, their permeability is determined by the weathering process. In these areas, the thickness of the permeable zone is assumed to be 50 meters.

The main boundary conditions include infiltration recharge uniformly applied to the entire model area and a river. Evapotranspiration is not specified since the water table in the alluvial horizon exceeds 5 meters based on known well depths. Most likely, the water table is at a depth where the influence of evapotranspiration only begins to manifest near streams and rivers. Additionally, for predictive modeling, two quarries are defined as drains, and for forecasting the dewatering of quarries, boundary conditions of "drain" and "well" are used.

The greatest uncertainty lies in the filtration properties of the deposits. According to the limited experimental filtration studies, the filtration coefficient (kf) for Quaternary deposits ranges from 3 to 62 m/day, and for sedimentary deposits, it ranges from 0.01 to 8.56 m/day. It can be assumed that a kf of around 1 m/day is due to a zone of increased fracturing near faults and mine workings, while the average values of the formation are $k = 0.04$ m/day. In this context, it is important to consider flooded workings. Over more than 25 years of mining, these mine workings have likely partially or completely collapsed, filled with loose material, and formed channels of increased permeability. Given the density and quantity of mine workings, it seems impractical to consider each one individually, and a general contour of the zone of increased permeability has been identified. It is assumed that in the zone of increased fracturing associated with underground workings, the filtration coefficient is increased by an order of magnitude compared to the surrounding rocks - up to 0.5 m/day and higher. More precise assessment of rock permeability in the disturbed zone can be conducted either during operation by monitoring the rate of water level decline in the quarry and in the formation, or by conducting additional hydrogeological experiments. One such large-scale experiment is planned for the summer of 2024 - pumping water from the shaft for 3 months to lower the water level in Quarry No. 1 by 30-50 meters and thus evaluate the permeability of the technologically disturbed formation.

Due to the extremely large difference in filtration coefficients, it is crucial to accurately account for the base of loose deposits in the model. For this purpose, a database of 1505 wells was analyzed and filtered. Interpolation of elevations with smoothing was carried out using the "kriging" algorithm (Kleijnen, 2017).

Development of a numerical model

The numerical model is being developed for the Modflow version 6 program. In the Quaternary deposits, there corresponds one, the uppermost computational layer. The aquifer system is divided into 20 computational layers for more accurate calculation of both water level recovery after cessation of dewatering and the forecast of water level decline after the start of pit dewatering.

The initial values of the filtration parameters are as mentioned above. One of the most important parameters that remains unsupported is the specific yield (water yield) of the rocks. It determines the total volume of water that needs to be pumped out to dewater the pit. While the volume of the pit itself is well known, the volume of water in the rocks can vary widely. The specific yield can be calibrated in the model based on measurements of water level recovery in the pits. Calibration was manually performed based on water level recovery in the Pit No.1 until 2017. The calibrated value of the specific yield for the native rocks was determined to be 1.2%. The specific yield of the loose Quaternary deposits was not calibrated and was set at 10%. A comparison of calculated and actual water levels at this value is shown in Figure 3, and a map of existing groundwater levels is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 3. Calculated and actual graphs of water level recovery in Pit No. 1

In the calibrated model, the primary task was to solve the predictive problem of estimating the volume of water inflows into Pit No. 1 during its dewatering process over the course of a year, and subsequently during its operation for 7 years.

Figure 4. Current calculated water table

Analysis of uncertainty in the forecasted water inflow volume

The accepted values of the geofiltration parameters are not strictly defined. During calibration, the actual known course of water level recovery in Pit No. 1 was reproduced. The relatively small number of observations on the groundwater conditions only allows for confirmation of the average values of the geofiltration parameters.

The filtration coefficient of sedimentary rocks is assumed to be 0.04 m/day; however, the possible range of its variability is expected to be no less than for the more studied loose rocks. Additionally, the rock mass has two types of disturbances - tectonic discontinuities and underground mining works. According to the analysis of archival tests, for most parameters, the range of variability reaches two orders of magnitude. As mentioned earlier, each excavation was not individually input into the model because there is no information on their current state. In the event of a collapse in the excavation, not only is the excavation itself filled with loose material, but the rock mass above the excavation is also destroyed, significantly increasing its permeability. The fact that the filtration coefficient in the disturbed zone is increased is not in doubt, but assuming an increase by an order of magnitude is an assumption.

During the exploration of deposits, around 60 individual tectonic disturbances were identified. Along each fault, there is a zone of increased fracturing, which is implemented in the model with a filtration coefficient of 0.5 m/day in a zone width of 25 m.

In these conditions, with insufficient justification of the geofiltration parameters, it is essential to assess the uncertainty of the forecast. One of the methods for assessing uncertainty for such nonlinear problems is the Monte Carlo method (Doherty, 2015). Applied to geofiltration models, the Monte Carlo method involves estimating the probability distribution of the predicted quantity by running the model multiple times with different sets of filtration parameters. This approach allows linking the uncertainty of the forecast to the uncertainty of the initial parameters. The uncertainty of the forecast is evaluated with respect to four parameters:

1. Gravitational water yield - 1.2% (range from 0.6 to 2.4% - doubled).
2. Filtration coefficient of undisturbed sedimentary deposits - 0.04 m/day (range from 0.01 to 0.16 m/day - quadrupled).
3. Filtration coefficient in fault zones - 0.5 m/day (0.1 - 2.5 m/day - fivefold).
4. Filtration coefficient in the zone of underground workings - 0.5 m/day (0.1 - 5 m/day).

For the four specified parameters, random samples within the accepted ranges were generated using the R language [www.R-project.org]. A normal distribution was chosen for the water yield, while a lognormal distribution was selected for the filtration coefficients, as it is considered more appropriate (Freeze, 1975; Gelhar et al., 1992; Sudicky, 1986). The distributions of the parameters are shown in Figure 5. A total of 500 random sets of the four parameters were created, and for each set, the dewatering of the Pit No.1 over one year was calculated.

Figure 5. Accepted density distribution of the four parameters

For the calculations, a local model (insert) was created, on which predictive calculations were performed for all 500 sets of key parameter values that were generated.

The results of the geofiltration predictive calculations

The obtained range of the probable volume of water that needs to be pumped out for the primary dewatering of Pit No. 1 closely matches the preliminary results obtained using a coarser regional model. The probability distribution follows a lognormal pattern with a median of 13.7 million cubic meters, as shown in Figure 6. From the figure, it is evident that the distribution is not entirely symmetrical. The minimum predicted water inflow is 9.75 million cubic meters, and there is no characteristic "tail" of improbable values typically seen in random distributions that extends towards higher values. This is because a significant portion of the water (approximately 8.95 million cubic meters) is already present in the quarry in a free state, and the calculated volume of pumped water cannot be lower than this amount.

Figure 6. Probability density histogram of the predicted water volume

In the constructed local model, forecasts were also made for water inflows during the pit's deepening in the first 7 years of its development after the initial year of dewatering, totaling 8 years. Due to space constraints, a detailed description of the results is omitted in this work. It can be mentioned that the average daily water inflows increase from 8.5 to 16 thousand cubic meters. As part of the predictive calculations, the potential effectiveness of an anti-filtration curtain between Pit No. 1 and the river was evaluated. Stochastic modeling results indicated that with the maximum curtain length, the reduction in water inflows would not exceed 13% of the total water inflow, making it an ineffective solution. Additionally, a negative emergency scenario was quantitatively assessed, involving a breakthrough of underground mining workings connecting quarries and the flooding of Pit No. 1. Several non-stationary scenarios were solved, resulting in an additional water inflow ranging from 24 to 75 thousand cubic meters per day.

The results of geomigration modelling

Changes in salinity over time have been calculated using a numerical geomechanical migration model. In Modflow version 6, the geomechanical modeling module is already included in the program, and the transition to the migration model is made with minimal changes. The only migration parameter used is the effective porosity (n_a), which is set to $n_a = 0.025$ for Mesozoic terrigenous and sedimentary-

volcanogenic formations. Since the main modeled component is total salinity and processes such as sorption that affect the concentration of dissolved substances were not considered, dispersion was not specified. Salinity is modeled as a single component, given in units of g/L. Additionally, the pH value is modeled, which is given in dimensionless units.

Based on the provided information, four zones with different characteristics have been identified:

1. Pit No. 1 and No. 2: Salinity (M) = 6 g/l, pH = 2.
2. Rock mass disturbed by underground workings: pH = 4.5, Variable salinity (M) ranging from 4.5 to 12 g/l.
3. Undisturbed rock mass: Salinity (M) = 4 g/l, pH = 4.5.
4. Groundwater alluvial aquifer: Salinity (M) = 0.3 g/l, pH = 6.

Under these conditions, a predictive calculation has been performed. Due to the mixing of water from different zones, the salinity and pH of the water extracted from the quarry gradually change. The calculation results are presented in Figure 7. The graph shows only the first year because the most significant changes occur during the initial period. In the first few days, some decrease in salinity is expected due to the activation of water inflow from the groundwater aquifer. Then, the inflow of water from the disturbed rock mass surrounding the quarry gradually increases, leading to salinity even exceeding the initial values. Subsequently, a linear decrease in salinity is established, which ultimately decreases to 5.2 g/l and does not reach 4 g/l during the quarry deepening period. The pH stabilizes by the end of the first year and reaches a value of 4.5 pH units.

Figure 7. Predictive graph of changes in composition parameters during the dewatering of Pit No. 1

CONCLUSION

The present study presents the results of research conducted using geofiltration and geomigration modeling. Due to the unknown condition of abandoned underground workings and the disturbed rock mass, there is uncertainty in the magnitude of predicted water inflows. This uncertainty is assessed using the Monte Carlo method. Additionally, a predictive calculation of possible emergency scenarios involving the breakthrough of water from Pit No. 2 into Pit No. 1 was conducted on the geofiltration model. Based on the geofiltration model, a geomigration model was constructed, and a predictive task regarding changes in salinity and pH during quarry operation was solved.

In the summer of 2024, a large-scale experimental filtration study is planned, the results of which will help increase the accuracy and reduce uncertainty in the presented predictive calculations.

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